

Intertextuality in Chinua Achebe's *No Longer at Ease*

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Abstract

This paper critically examines the centrality of intertextuality in the appreciation of Chinua Achebe's No Longer at Ease (1960). Achebe includes a pertinent example of epigraph in his novel. He quotes from T.S.Eliot, whose poem mirrors the postcolonial condition that is explored at length in his novel. “The Journey of the Magi” deals with the difficult journey of the Biblical Magi or Wise Men as they searched for Christ. Their journey parallels the Protagonist, Obi Okonkwo's journey from Nigeria to England and then back to Nigeria. He finds himself no longer at ease with his fellow countrymen and his culture. His estrangement from his culture is the same problem that thousands of Africans and Indians faced after their western education. They are not comfortable with their own culture and at the same time they are not willingly follow the new culture that they had embraced. This paper therefore attempts to explore that Achebe's No Longer at Ease (1960) reflects the post colonial complications and also ventures to highlight that the epigraph illuminates important aspect of the novel.

Keywords: intertextuality, epigraph, post colonial condition, estrangement, journey.

The term ‘intertextuality’, was coined by co-structural feminist critic Julia Kristeva in 1966. It means in general the shaping of one text's meaning by the other text. It refers both to the author's borrowing and manipulation of a prior text, and to the readers' reference to other texts in order to understand one text. The meaning is not transferred directly from writer to the reader. It is mediated through or filtered by ‘codes’ conveyed to the writer and the reader by the other text. Intertextuality is not just recognition that one text informs another text, rather it is an acknowledgement that one text transform another text; To quote Julia Kristeva:

If one grants that every signifying practice is a field of transpositions of various signifying system (an inter-textuality), then one understands that its “place” of enunciation and its denoted “object” are never single, complete, and identical to themselves, but always plural, shattered, capable of being tabulated. (Revolution in Poetic Language 60)

In theorizing intertextuality, Kristeva maintains that every text is constituted “by a mosaic of citations, every text is absorption and another text” (The Kristeva Reader 37). Like Kristeva, Terry Eagleton in his book “Literary Theory: An Introduction” opines that every literary work is essentially “re-written” (192). In re-writing literary works as Eagleton indicates, each text directly or indirectly makes reference to other texts, this is what Peter Barry sees as: “a

major degree of reference between one text and another” (91). In his important work, “The Theory of the Text” Barthes lends credence to this perspective:

Any text is an intertext; other texts are present in it, at varying levels, in more or less recognizable forms: the text of the previous and surrounding culture. Any text is a new tissue of past citations. Bits of codes, formulate, rhythmic models, fragments of social languages, etc. pass into the text and are redistributed within it. [...] Epistemologically, the concept of intertext is what brings to the theory of the text the volume of sociality. (39)

Intertextuality then, yields to plurality of texts.

We returned to our places, these Kingdoms,
But no longer at ease here, in the old dispensation,
With an alien people clutching their gods.
I should be glad of another death.

-T. S. Eliot, “The Journey of the Magi”

The title for the novel comes from this selection of verses by T.S.Eliot, an early twentieth century American expatriate poet who eventually becomes a naturalized British citizen. The choice of the poem “The Journey of the Magi” is very much apt. it is a poem about how spiritual birth can feel like death. Even though they are being born into something new, they are still witnessing the death of their old way of life, and their old beliefs. This process is painful. Even Achebe accepts this in his interview with Jerome Brooks explained thus:

I think the poem from which I took the title of No Longer at Ease, the one about the three magi, is one of the great poems in the English language. These people who went and then came back to their countries were “no longer at ease” ... I think that that is great- the use of simple language, even when things talked about are profound, very moving, very poignant. So that’s really all there is to it.

“The Journey of the Magi” details the journey of the Biblical magi (or “Wise men) as they searched for Christ. The three magi saw a brilliant new star in the east and realized it signaled the birth of a new king. They followed it until they found Jesus, and they worshipped his as their king. In this poem the speaker talks about how the journey was difficult: it was bitterly cold and there were many times they regretted it. They had all these memories of home, where they enjoyed warm weather and “silken girls bringing sherbet,” when they finally reached their destination, a humble tavern and a stable where Jesus is born, they wondered where their journey was for a birth or a death. They had met the Messiah and though the meeting was a birth, it was a bitter birth, one more like death than birth. In the verses excerpted here, the speaker returned to a fixed place they could call home but realized that after a pilgrimage such a place no longer exists, that the old dispensation has been disturbed, that death is the only certainty in a world where the worship of new gods has destroyed the old spiritual framework. The speaker would be glad for “another death” like the one just experienced, perhaps because they he would feel at ease again in his old life with his family and friends.

These short verses, the final verses of the poem, describe what many writers and literary critics have called the postcolonial condition. The journey that the magi took parallels Obi Okokwo’s journey from his home to England, where he experiences an intellectual and cultural birth that is more like death. When he returns to his home country, Nigeria, he feels culturally displaced. He is “no longer at ease” among his countrymen, with their religion and their way of life. Not only does Obi judge their lack of education, but he also feels many of their other customs are barbaric and should be eradicated as citizens embrace Christianity and western education.

In one sense, the title suggests something obvious – someone once felt comfortable and is now feeling uneasy. And actually, once the reader gets into the novel, he or she finds out that this quick assessment is accurate. The title reflects the discomfort felt by the main character, Obi Okonkwo. His university education in England has left him feeling alienated from his family and friends. While in England, he was alone in a foreign place, thousands of miles from his family, speaking a

foreign tongue. And besides all that, he comes from a warm, tropical place, and needs to adjust to living in cold, foggy, rainy England. Obi can no longer get his mother's pounded foo-foo, yam, or fish soup. Instead, he has had to adjust to eating boiled potatoes, boiled meat, and boiled vegetables.

But that is not actually Obi's problem. It gets a little more complicated than that. The problem of homesickness is compounded by the fact that Obi partly rejected his own culture, embracing Western values through his Western education. As a result of his Christian upbringing and his British education, Obi decided that the written word is the way to go. He suddenly found himself believing in democracy and thinking that if he wanted to get ahead in the world, he need to be a Christian, read and write proper English, and behave like a European.

So he tried. But that does not mean that he felt comfortable in England. There he was, studying in an alien culture, feeling uncomfortable and different. However, when he returns to Nigeria, not only does he not fit with his fellow countrymen, but also uncomfortable among the English expatriates in Nigeria, even though they all work together and they are supposed to be buddies. He does not feel contended with his own folks and he does not feel at ease with the other guys, either. Obi's estrangement from his culture is the same problem that thousands of young people in Africa and India faced after their western education. On the one hand, they saw all sorts of problems with the culture they had left behind; on the other hand, they were not accepted by the western culture they had tried to embrace.

This is a phenomenon explored by many postcolonial writers. Colonial powers expended a great deal of effort and energy towards distinguishing between western culture and colonized cultures; western literature, philosophy, and popular culture portrayed colonized cultures as "inferior." Young people from colonized countries felt estranged from their own culture after their western education, even while they were not accepted by westerners. This condition has been called a "postcolonial identity" and Obi exhibits a classic case of it. As Simon Gikandi rightly points out: "Obi returned to the dangerous zone of 'occult instability' (80) between the African and colonial cultures.

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